

THE PROBLEM OF MOTHERHOOD IN THE WORKS OF MODERN WOMEN WRITERS

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Abstract

Motherhood is a topic that has been explored in literature for centuries, but in recent times, contemporary female writers have approached the subject with a renewed vigor. The complexities and challenges of motherhood have been given greater attention, with authors exploring the joys and struggles of motherhood in their works. Many writers have approached the topic with a fresh perspective, often challenging traditional narratives and expectations surrounding motherhood. Some notable authors who have delved into this theme include Rachel Cusk, Sheila Heti, Maggie Nelson, Meena Kandasamy, Sayaka Murata, and Maye Musk. In this article, we will examine the problem of motherhood in the works of some of contemporary female writers of the world who have contributed to the discourse on the subject.

Key words: modern world literature, contemporary female writers, motherhood in literature, the problem of motherhood.

The role of women writers has changed significantly in the 21st century. Thanks to the Internet, social media, and the growth of digital publishing platforms, female writers are now more visible than ever before. This has opened up opportunities for more women to be published, and to have their work seen and heard by a wider audience. As a result, a greater diversity of women's voices appeared in literature, as women writers from different ethnicities, cultures, and backgrounds have been given a platform to tell their stories. This has led to a greater understanding and appreciation of the experiences of women from different parts of the world.

Nowadays women writers are challenging traditional gender stereotypes and representations of women in literature. They are creating complex, multi-dimensional female characters who defy expectations and show that there is no one "right" way to be a woman. There are many more exciting themes being explored by 21st-century female writers: the ways in which race, gender, sexuality, class, and other aspects of identity intersect and impact a person's experiences; a growing awareness of mental health issues in society; a broad range of gender and sexuality themes, from LGBT representation to the exploration of traditional gender roles; immigration, displacement, privacy, surveillance, and social media. But there is a theme that remains eternal for women writers around the world: the theme of motherhood.

In recent years, the theme of motherhood has become an increasingly important subject in literature, with contemporary female writers exploring the complexities of this experience in new and powerful ways. Many writers have approached the topic with a fresh perspective, often challenging traditional narratives and expectations surrounding motherhood. Some notable authors who have delved into this theme include Rachel Cusk, Sheila Heti, Maggie Nelson, Meena Kandasamy, Sayaka Murata, and Maye Musk. These writers have contributed significant insights and perspectives on the challenges and rewards of motherhood, making important contributions to contemporary literature.

Rachel Cusk is a British author who has made significant contributions to the exploration of motherhood in contemporary literature. Her trilogy of novels (Cusk, 2014), which includes "Outline," "Transit," and "Kudos," explore the experiences of a writer and mother as she navigates the complexities of motherhood, marriage, and personal identity. Through these novels, Cusk delves into the challenges and contradictions of motherhood, including the tension between selfhood and motherhood, and the loss of autonomy that can accompany the experience of motherhood. Cusk's works offer a nuanced and insightful exploration of the complex and often conflicting emotions and experiences associated with motherhood, and her trilogy has been highly praised by critics for its unique perspective and innovative approach to the subject.

Sheila Heti is a Canadian writer who has explored the topic of motherhood in her novel, "Motherhood" (Heti, 2019). The novel centers around the experiences of a woman who is grappling with the decision of whether or not to have a child, and the complex emotions and societal expectations that come with this decision. Heti's novel raises important questions about the role of motherhood in women's lives, and the pressures and expectations that can often be associated with it. Through her protagonist's introspective journey, Heti examines the ways in which motherhood can both enrich and complicate a woman's life, and explores the societal expectations that often place motherhood at the center of women's identity.

Maggie Nelson is an American writer who has examined the topic of motherhood in her memoir, "The Argonauts" (Nelson, 2015). The memoir is a genre-bending work that combines personal narrative, cultural criticism, and theory to explore Nelson's experiences of pregnancy, motherhood, and gender identity. Through her memoir, Nelson challenges traditional notions of gender and motherhood, offering a powerful critique of the ways in which these concepts have been constructed and enforced by society. She also explores the challenges of queer parenthood, and the ways in which this experience can complicate and enrich our understanding of family and love. "The Argonauts" is widely regarded as a groundbreaking work.

Meena Kandasamy is an Indian writer who has reviewed the theme of motherhood in the novel, "When I Hit You" (Kandasamy, 2018). The novel is a powerful and harrowing account of domestic violence, told from the perspective of a woman who is trapped in an abusive marriage. Through her protagonist's experiences, Kandasamy explores the intersection of motherhood, gender, and violence, highlighting the ways in which motherhood can be both a source of strength and a source of vulnerability for women. She also examines the complex power dynamics that exist within intimate relationships, and the ways in which these dynamics can be shaped by societal expectations and cultural norms. "When I Hit You" is a searing indictment of the violence and abuse that many women face in their personal lives. The novel is a powerful exploration of the complexity of motherhood and the challenges faced by women in abusive relationships.

In Japanese literature, the problem of motherhood has been explored by Sayaka Murata in her novel "Convenience Store Woman" (Murata, 2018). The novel follows the life of a woman who works at a convenience store and faces pressure from society to conform to traditional gender roles, including becoming a mother. Murata's exploration of motherhood is a critique of the societal expectations placed on women and the challenges faced by women who choose not to conform to these expectations.

Maye Musk is a well-known South African-born Canadian model and author who has revealed the topic of motherhood in her memoir, "A Woman Makes a Plan" (Musk, 2020). The memoir is a candid and reflective account of Musk's life and experiences as a mother to three children. Through her memoir, Musk discusses the challenges and joys of motherhood, the importance of balance, and the role of resilience in overcoming obstacles. She also reflects on the ways in which her own experiences as a mother have shaped her personal and professional life, and offers insights into how women can navigate the complexities of motherhood while pursuing their own goals and aspirations. "A Woman Makes a Plan" is an inspiring and empowering memoir that highlights the importance of motherhood in shaping women's lives, and has been praised by readers for its honesty, authenticity, and relatable portrayal of the joys and challenges of motherhood.

Musk's book is the example of the growing interest among female writers in exploring the complexities of motherhood. Other contemporary female writers who have studied the problem of motherhood have approached the topic of motherhood from different angles, but all share a deep understanding of the challenges and joys of motherhood.

In conclusion, the problem of motherhood has been explored by contemporary women writers from all over the world. These writers have provided fresh perspectives on a subject that has been explored in literature for centuries, capturing the complexity and nuance of the experience of motherhood. Through their works, they have challenged traditional notions of motherhood and examined the impact of societal expectations on women.

Contemporary literature is depicting a more diverse range of mothers, including single mothers, same-sex parents, working mothers, adoptive mothers, and mothers with disabilities. This diversity allows for a more nuanced and complex understanding of motherhood. Women writers are challenging traditional narratives of motherhood that portray mothers as selfless and sacrificing, and instead are exploring the complexities and challenges of motherhood, including the experiences of postpartum depression, infertility, and the struggle to balance work and family. Many women writers are exploring the ways in which motherhood can be a source of strength and resilience, especially in the face of adversity. Literature is criticising societal expectations of motherhood, including the pressure to be a perfect mother, the assumption that motherhood is the primary role for a woman, and the lack of support for mothers in society.

Rachel Cusk, Sheila Heti, Maggie Nelson, Meena Kandasamy, Sayaka Murata, and Maye Musk have each brought their unique perspectives and experiences to this important and complex subject. These writers have made important contributions to the ongoing conversation about motherhood and its place in contemporary society, and have demonstrated the importance of female voices in shaping our understanding of this vital subject.

As more women continue to write about motherhood, we can expect to gain a deeper understanding of this essential and transformative experience, valuable sources of insight and inspiration on the topic of motherhood, and the work of female writers will undoubtedly continue to shape and influence our understanding of this important subject for years to come.

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